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GLOBAL COOPERATION FOR THE RESTORATION OF THE ARAL SEA REGION: OPPORTUNITIES AND LIMITATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This article talks about the Aral Sea, which was one of the biggest lakes in the world before. By early 2000s, it became one of the most serious environmental problems of the 21st century. This disaster did not only affect Central Asian countries, but also had influence on other parts of the world, such as Europe and even the United States.

The article explains how international cooperation helps to improve the Aral Sea area and what problems still exist. The study shows that global support made some positive changes in environment and people's life conditions. However, there are still many issues like lack of money, political problems, and long-term sustainability.

In conclusion, the article says that global cooperation is important, but it should be combined with responsibility from regional countries to restore the Aral Sea area.

Keywords: cotton policy, saxaul, economic stability, desert, salty lands, political interests, financial problems, diseases.

INTRODUCTION

The Aral Sea used to be the fourth largest inland water area in the world and it had a very big importance for ecological and economic balance of Central Asia. But

from the 1960s, too much water was diverted from the Amu Darya and Syr Darya rivers for agricultural purposes, mainly for cotton growing. Because of this action, the sea reduced rapidly in size. This situation caused serious ecological, social and economic crisis in the Aral Sea region.

Because the sea dried up, many thousands of square kilometers changed into a salty desert. Plants and animals were reduced strongly, and salt mixed with toxic dust started to spread by storms. These dust storms became dangerous for people's health and caused problems like birth issues. The Aral Sea crisis seriously affected public health, which shows the need to improve healthcare systems with help from international organizations. Due to this situation, respiratory diseases, heart problems, and child death rates increased.

There are several reasons for the drying of the Aral Sea. One of the main causes was the policy of the former Soviet system. It followed a very risky irrigation strategy and took water directly from the Amu Darya and Syr Darya rivers. This water was used mostly for cotton fields, so it could not reach the Aral Sea anymore. As a result, the water level of the sea dropped very fast. This environmental problem attracted attention from the international community.

Organizations like the United Nations, the World Bank, and the European Union started to support projects to improve the Aral Sea region. Some technical actions, such as building dams, embankments, and planting saxaul trees, together with international funding, showed that local living conditions can be improved. The role of global cooperation, its opportunities, and also its limits in restoring the Aral Sea region are discussed.

NASA's Terra and Aqua satellites have been documenting the ongoing shrinkage of the Aral Sea since 2000. Image credit: NASA Goddard Photo and Video License: CC BY 2.0

METHODS

This article uses qualitative research methods. It is based on analysis of scientific papers, official reports, policy documents, and data from international organizations. The main sources include reports from the United Nations, the World Bank, the International Fund for Saving the Aral Sea, and national environmental institutions.

During the research, a comparative scientific method was used. Different ecological and social projects carried out by various countries and organizations were compared. It was pointed out that international cooperation and monitoring systems for the Aral Sea, such as forecasting water distribution, can help to decrease conflicts between sides. Also, programs focused on improving public health were studied separately. This research method helped to analyze the Aral Sea problem more fully from ecological, political, and social-economic points of view.

RESULTS

One of the biggest results of global cooperation is that the Aral Sea problem started to receive more attention from the international community. This attention can be seen through financial help, technical assistance, and scientific recommendations. Many projects supported by international organizations are trying to bring back ecological balance in the Aral Sea region. According to researcher Elena A. Zonn, who studies water resources and regional policy, political cooperation and coordination between institutions are very important when solving environmental problems.

Planting saxaul and other plants that can survive in desert conditions on the dried seabed has become one of the most effective solutions. These plants help to reduce dust storms and protect the soil from erosion. Because these projects were carried out with international support, large territories could be covered. Some geographers who studied the historical reasons of the Aral Sea disaster say that international help is necessary, but without serious changes in regional water policies and water management, full recovery will not be possible.

So, what really caused this tragedy? Many specialists agree that the main reason for the drying of the Aral Sea was the wrong use and unfair distribution of water resources. For many centuries, the Amu Darya and Syr Darya rivers were the main sources of water for the Aral Sea. In the past, these rivers brought around 60 cubic kilometers of water to the sea every year. Today, this amount has dropped sharply and is only about 5 cubic kilometers per year, which is not enough to support the sea.

These major rivers of Central Asia start in very high mountain areas such as the Hindu Kush, the Pamirs, and the Tien Shan. After flowing more than two thousand kilometers through countries like Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, and Uzbekistan, they used to end in the Aral Sea. Besides the already mentioned reasons, some researchers think that changes in the seabed layers also played a role. They believe that water may be leaking underground toward the Caspian Sea and nearby lakes. Other experts argue that global climate change is the main cause, especially because glaciers in the mountains are melting, and these glaciers feed both the Amu Darya and Syr Darya rivers.

Another reason for writing this article is that sciences such as oceanography and river studies are still not well developed in our country. For many years, this type of research was mainly done by foreign specialists, often based on their own interests. Therefore, in this article, we also had to rely on information provided by them. Still, the Aral Sea is an important part of our national history. At least basic knowledge about it should belong to us, and in reality, we should know much more than only general facts.

Historical sources show that about twenty million years ago, the Aral Sea and the Caspian Sea were connected. In addition, ancient burial sites found on the dried seabed date back to the middle of the first millennium. This proves that even in ancient times, the Aral Sea had periods when it became smaller and shallow, before filling again later.

In the 21st century, climate change in the Aral Sea region has become faster and more noticeable. Large water bodies always played an important role in keeping climate balance. The Aral Sea helped to control weather conditions by reducing cold Siberian winds in winter and cooling extreme summer heat. After the sea started disappearing, agriculture suffered more from frost damage, and livestock conditions became worse.

If these effects were limited only to the Aral Sea region, the situation would be less serious. However, today the impact covers a very wide area. Strong winds lift huge amounts of salt, chemicals, and toxic dust from the dried seabed into the air. These harmful particles travel long distances and reach not only other parts of Asia but also

Europe. When salty rain and snow fall back to the ground, they damage ecosystems and negatively affect nature wherever they land.

[5].

In addition, global cooperation has helped introduce advanced practices for efficient water resource management. The adoption of modern irrigation technologies has reduced water waste and increased sustainability in agriculture. International cooperation and monitoring systems for the Aral Sea (e.g., water allocation forecasting) can help reduce conflicts [2].

Restoration efforts around the Aral Sea highlight the need for agroforestry, salinity management, and transformation of local agriculture—meaning that ecological and social solutions must go hand in hand. In the social sphere, international programs supporting healthcare, education, and employment have contributed to improving the living standards of the local population [1, 3, 4].

The desiccation of the Aral Sea does not rely on a single cause, according to many studies. In addition to the human factor (the flawed policies of the old system), it can also be viewed as a cyclical natural phenomenon. Its negative impacts on multiple regions have contributed to its interpretation as a global problem. Material incentives provided by the World Bank and numerous organizations have played a major role in greening the Aral Sea and its surroundings, particularly by significantly reducing the rise of saline particles through saxaul planting.

DISCUSSION

Global cooperation faces a number of serious limitations. One of the main problems is the complexity of regional water policy. Since several countries depend on the Amu Darya and Syr Darya basins, disagreements over water use frequently arise [3]. Financial sustainability is also a significant issue. Many projects depend on

external funding, and there is a risk that they will halt if resources decrease. Furthermore, some programs are oriented toward short-term results and are not sufficiently integrated to ensure long-term ecological stability [11].

As students of interpreting, we looked at this global problem from different points of view. The results show that although global cooperation plays an important role in restoring the Aral Sea region, it cannot give enough results without strong regional political support and active participation of local people [1], [9]. As some researchers point out, international help is necessary, but without changes in regional policies and better management of water resources, real recovery will not happen. Because of this, international projects should be planned by considering local needs and social conditions.

Moreover, the process of ecological restoration should be connected with economic development. Creating new and alternative sources of income for local population is very important to reduce migration from the Aral Sea region and to achieve long-term sustainable development [11].

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The table above clearly shows how the water level of the Aral Sea changed during different years. From the data, it can be seen that the sea level passed through several stages, from stage 1 to stage 8. These stages show that the level of the sea did not stay stable all the time, but increased and decreased in different periods. This change happened because of different factors, especially climate conditions and the use of water resources. In the 1960s, the Aral Sea level was still relatively stable. However, starting from this period, a sharp decline can be observed. Sadly, this decrease was not a natural process, but mainly caused by human activities.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, the restoration of the Aral Sea region is a very complicated and long-term process, and it cannot be completed without global cooperation. Even though international organizations and different countries have provided important support, problems such as financial shortages, political challenges, and institutional limitations are still present.

In the future, successful restoration of the Aral Sea region will require stronger global cooperation combined with regional responsibility, sustainable water policies, and active involvement of local people. The Aral Sea issue is not only an environmental problem, but also a wider international challenge that needs joint efforts and cooperation. This process takes a long time and needs careful planning and strategic partnership. Although many international organizations and foreign countries are trying to help, limited financial resources continue to slow down progress.

Therefore, the main focus in the future should be on creating a sustainable water management policy. Rational use of water resources, fair and scientific control of river flows, and shared responsibility among regional countries are extremely important. At the same time, residents should not be excluded from this process, but should take an active role in decision-making and implementation. In conclusion, the restoration of the Aral Sea region can achieve long-lasting results only when global cooperation is supported by strong regional political will, effective governance, and local participation. Only this approach can ensure real ecological and social recovery of the Aral Sea region.

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